

LANGUAGE FEATURES OF TED TALKS AND WAYS OF THEIR TRANSMISSION INTO THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Feruzakhon Mansurova

Independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11116492>

Abstract. The aim of this research is to determine the linguistic features of online TED Talks videos and analysis of how they are transmitted from the English language into Uzbek. To achieve this goal successfully, the researcher includes distinctive language features of TED Talks video, selection of contextual examples illustrating highlighted linguistic features and analysis of the preservation of selected features in the translation of lectures into Uzbek. Research material analyses one video lecture in English taken from the official website of TED Talks as well as its Uzbek translation which was dedicated to the greatest risk of global catastrophe.

Keywords: public lecture, TED Talks, language features, translation transformations.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays as lectures have ceased to be only an academic phenomenon, they are gradually spreading among people in offline and online modes. Such lectures today have become popular not only among specialists in certain local area but also among ordinary people around the world. In order to share different topics with public, TED Talks are considered to be the most popular format of delivering public speech. TED Talks platform (Technology Entertainment Design), which was created in is subscribed and viewed by millions of people in the world. The aim of the project is to spread unique ideas. Motivational speech by famous speakers, interesting topics, optimal length of lectures, availability of multilingual translation caused public interest and contributed to the expansion of audience including people in Uzbekistan. All these reasons led to further studying the linguistic features of the format and the problems of their transfer to the Uzbek language. Therefore, there is a request for high-quality of lecture translations into Uzbek. TED Talks lecture format has already become the subject study of research in some investigations of some linguists such as Caliendo G, Compagnone A. [1, 105-122], Nazirova R. [6, 45], Nechaeva N. [7, 17], Scotto di C.G [9, 23-34].

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS

However, in this aspect first, ISM Viktorova [8, 254] sorted out linguistic features of the TED Talks lecture format, namely, more frequent use of addresses, questions, personal pronouns first and second person, imperatives, modal verbs, introductory expressions, emotive vocabulary, tropes, common colloquial expressions and aphorisms. In fact, TEDx Talks's YouTube Channel has 38,800,000 subscribers with 202,117 videos uploaded so far (video lectures are shorter than 18 minutes) and the overall channel views are 7.4 B according to 2023 statistics [2].

For practical justification of the analysis of the above features of TED Talks, the researcher uses the video which is presented by a world famous philanthropist Bill Gates on March 2015 named "The next outbreak? We are not ready" watched by 44, 918, 206 views [5].

The examples of contextual use were selected from the material of the video lecture. For this purpose, the researcher calculated the relative percentage of saturation textuality of the text by lexical, grammatical or syntactic units of every kind. For this, personal pronouns, imperatives, modal verbs, introductory expressions, questions, tropes, and emotive lexical units were divided by the number of sentences in the text of the lecture. The calculated numbers were multiplied by one hundred. The results of the performed calculations are demonstrated in figure 1.

The highlighted features of the TED Talks lecture format

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data gathered illustrate the highlighted features of TED Talks lectures. The translated and transcribed format of the selected material was also investigated. In its original video with English transcription, the speaker conducts more informal conversation in a relaxed, friendly manner. However, such appeals are more often omitted when the speech was translated into Uzbek which means that the translator maintained more neutral style. For example: **“When I was a kid, the disaster we worried about most was a nuclear war”**. The first person singular pronoun, **“ I ”** is often used to imitate non-forced conversation to tell a story and share personal experience. Nevertheless, in many cases, when translated into Uzbek, this pronoun is omitted and replaced by the first person plural pronoun, **“ we ”**. For instance : **“Bolalik davrimizda biz hammasidan ham yadroviy urush boshlanishidan qo'rqar edik.**

The speaker often addresses the audience with a pronoun second person **“you”**, which in most cases is lost in translation, for example: **“ You can have a virus where people feel well enough while they're infectious that they get on a plane or they go to a market”**. Omitting the second pronoun **“you”** really affects certain changes in meaning in the statement.

“Keyingi virus shunday bo'lishi mumkinki, kasallanganlarda samolyot orqali sayohat qilishga yoki bozorlarga borishga kuch bo'lishi mumkin”. In the next example, **“you”** is also omitted in the translation with some changes: **“And as you look at what went on, the problem wasn't that there was a system that didn't work well enough, the problem was that we didn't have a system at all”**. In Uzbek it is written as follows: **“Bunday bir holatda, muammo - tizimning yaxshi ishlamasligida emas, bunday tizimning o'zi mavjud emasligida edi”**.

The first pronoun of plural form **“we”** is used to show unity with the audience that is listening to the speaker, or to report your membership in a research team which gives a higher reliability of information presented to the audience. A tendency to partial omission of the pronoun **“we”** is visible when the speech was translated into Uzbek, which also brings more formal style, for example: **“First, we need strong health systems in poor countries”**. In the Uzbek translation it says: **“Birinchidan, kambag'al davlatlarda kuchli sog'liqni saqlash tizimini yaratish kerak”**. Another example is: **“We don't have to hoard cans of spaghetti or go down into the basement.”** However, in Uzbek, omitting the pronoun **“we”** makes the translated meaning more formal: **“Makaronlar bilan zahiralanişga va yerto'lada yashirinishga ham ehtiyoj yo'q”**. This change

can really be seen in the third example: *"We need to do simulations, germ games, not war games, so that we see where the holes are"*. In the Uzbek language, it says: *"Tayyorgarlik mashg'ulotlari o'tkazish kerak — harbiy mashg'ulotlar emas, bakteriologik; zaif tomonlarni aniqlab olish uchun"*.

In total, **58** personal pronouns were found in the studied material, used as the subject, of which 7 pronouns **I**, 31 pronouns **we**, 6 pronouns **you**, 4 pronouns **they**, 10 pronouns **it**. Thus, there is a loss of 40% for **we**, 25% for **I**, 30% for **you**. Thus, when translating the English speech to Uzbek, there is a notable depersonalization of the formation by replacing sentences with personal pronouns.

More clearly, statistical data on the frequency of use and translation of personal pronouns in the nominative case in TED Talks video are presented in figure 2.

Interrogative constructions that are quite often used by the lecturer helps emphasize the importance of the presented issue, attract and retain the listeners' attention. For example: *"NATO does a lot of war games to check, are people well trained? Do they understand about fuel and logistics and the same radio frequencies?"*. The speaker utilizes questions in TED Talks video to create a question-answer form of presentation, conveys the dialogic nature of the original verbal utterance and creates an illusion of a conversation with the audience. In these examples found, the preservation of the interrogative construct is observed. However, in the Uzbek translation, most of the interrogative sentences were replaced by affirmative sentences by omitting the interrogative meaning. For instance, *"NATO harbiy tayyorgarlikni tekshirish uchun ko'plab sinovlar o'tkazadi. Yoqilg'i, logistika va radioto'lqinlari haqidagi bilimlari tekshiriladi"*.

The imperative mood (imperative) in the studied material is used with incentive offers *"Let's..."* which is used to challenge the audience to take action, for example: *"Let's look at Ebola. I'm sure all of you read about it in the newspaper, lots of tough challenges"*. In some cases when translating into Uzbek *"Masalan, Ebola virusini olsak. Aminmanki, hammangiz bu haqda gazetalarda o'qigansiz - u juda ko'p muammolar olib keldi"*.

In the research material, some samples of modal verbs were found. In particular, **6** cases of modal verbs are used: 6 cases of **could**, 1 case of **might**, 9 cases of **can**, one case of **do not have to** and 3 cases of **need**.

3 cases of the modal verb **"should"** are used to persuade the listener for a particular action action. *"So this is a serious problem. We should be concerned"*. In the Uzbek translation, although the meaning of the statement was maintained, it is translated with the help of using another negative form but meaning the same: *"Bu jiddiy muammo. Biz bunga bee'tibor bo'lmasligimiz kerak."*

6 cases of using the modal verb “could” warns the listeners some possible predictions about the future by saying : *“The source of the virus could be a natural epidemic like Ebola, or it could be bioterrorism”*. Accordingly, in the Uzbek translation, it also tries to warn the listeners about some predictions that might happen in the future: *“Virus Ebolaga o'xshash tabiatga ega bo'lishi ham mumkin, yoki bioterroristlar tomonidan yaratilishi mumkin”*.

In 9 cases of the use of the modal verb “can”, 5 of them were used to encourage the listeners that they have the ability to make changes and take serious actions about the future, for example: *“But in fact, we can build a really good response system”*.

“That's where mothers can give birth safely, kids can get all their vaccines”. In some of the Uzbek translations, there is a little loss of modality “can” because it not only also emphasizes ability but also strengthens the meaning of the utterance *“Lekin bizning haqiqatdan ham samarador tizim yaratishga kuchimiz yetadi. Onalar xavfsiz tug'a olishi va go'daklar barcha vaksinalarni ola olishi uchun”*.

Introductory expressions play an important role in the studied lectures. They show the reliability of the information and the author’s confidence in this (**really, certainly**), the author’s doubt (**maybe, might be**), convey reasoning logic (**firstly, next time**), express reality (**in fact**), introduce effect or conclusion (**as a result, so**). In most cases, introductory words are adequately translated into Uzbek preserving its meaning.

Emotive vocabulary and tropes help to achieve a better expressiveness of the presentation, increase the impact on the listener such as (**well, oh..**) and denoting emotions (**happy, worried, sad etc**).

In the analyzed TED Talks lecture by Bill Gates, the trope and figurative comparison are used. As we know, trope is ropes are a type of figurative language that allows the writer to create images for the reader [4]. For example, in the original text, the speaker says: *“Now, in the movies it's quite different. There's a group of handsome epidemiologists ready to go, they move in, they save the day, but that's just pure Hollywood”*. In the translation, the trope is preserved and translated directly by not trying to find an equivalent variant in the Uzbek language which reduces the power of influencing the emotions of the Uzbek listener making the text less expressive, for instance: *“Filmlarda odatda hammasi boshqacha. Yordamga bir guruh kelishgan epidemiologlar yuboriladi, ular yetib kelishadi, hammani qutqarishadi — lekin bu bor-yog'i Gollivud”*.

Starting the speech by demonstrating **realia** at the beginning of the lecture helps the speaker to achieve the atmosphere of the deep imagination about the topic that is being explained. In fact, realia means objects that are used by educators in education from real life objects to improve students’ memorization about the topic and strengthen students’ associations between words and the real object [3]. Bill Gates, in his TED Talks video brings “**barrel**” in order to achieve an atmosphere of trust, friendly conversation and to help the listeners imagine the time he was young. For example: *“When I was a kid, the disaster we worried about most was a nuclear war. That's why we had a barrel like this down in our basement, filled with cans of food and water”*. When uzbek listeners watch it, they also pay attention to the realia that is explained in this sentence: *“Bolalik davrimizda biz hammasidan ham yadroviy urush boshlanishidan qo'rqqar edik. Shu sabab hammaning yer to'lasida shu kabi suv va konservalar to'ldirilgan bochkalar bo'lar edi”*.

CONCLUSION

Summarizing the data obtained during the lecture analysis, it can be concluded that when translating the lectures of TED Talks, there are notable grammatical, lexical and semantic changes as well as depersonalization of the narrative due to the omission of pronouns in the process of replacing sentence with subject personal pronouns with impersonal structures which bring the text of the Uzbek translation closer to more academic format. In the translation of the imperative mood and modal verbs, the categoricalness of the statement increases but the meaning is maintained.
YANA QO‘SHISH KERAK.

REFERENCE

1. Caliendo G., Compagnone A. Expressing Epistemic Stance in University Lectures and TED TALKS: A Contrastive Corpus-Based Analysis // *Lingue e Linguaggi*. 2014; № 11. Pp. 105 – 122.
2. E-resource: <https://www.speakrj.com/audit/report/UCsT0YIqwnpJCM-mx7-gSA4Q/youtube>
3. E-resource : [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Realia_\(education\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Realia_(education)).
4. E-resource : <https://writingexplained.org/grammar-dictionary/trope>.
5. E-resource:
 - a. https://www.ted.com/talks/bill_gates_the_next_outbreak_we_re_not_ready/transcript?language=uz&subtitle=uz
6. Nazirova R.G., Назирова Р.Г., Гергель О.В. Использование стилистических средств в устной публичной речи (на примере TED Talks). *Вестник Башкирского государственного педагогического университета им. М. Акмуллы*. 2021; № 1 (58). Сс. 45 – 50.
7. Nechaeva N.V. Популярная публичная лекция жанра TALK: особенности языка и стиля. *Известия Российского государственного педагогического университета им. А.И. Герцена*. 2016; № 180. Сс.17 – 22.
8. Viktorova E.Yu. Викторова Е.Ю. Дискурсивно-прагматическая специфика жанра лекции TED talk (сквозь призму функционирования в ней дискурсивов). *Жанры речи*. 2019; № 4 (24). Сс. 254 – 266.
9. Scotto di C.G. Pathos as a Communicative Strategy for Online Knowledge Dissemination: The Case of TED Talks. *Language, Linguistics, Literature. The Southeast Asian Journal of English Language Studies*. 2015; № 1 (21). P.p. 23 – 34.